

Fatigue Properties of CF/GF Hybrid Composites with the Respectively Equal Flexural Rigidity

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ABSTRACT

The fundamental investigation was made to develop the light weight spring materials with excellent spring properties from the hybrid composites of glass/epoxy (GRP) and carbon/epoxy (CRP) laminates. And in this paper, we calculated the relation between the flexural rigidity of the hybrid laminates and the spring constant using the number of plies as the structural factor of laminates. The result agreed with the experimental value. Furthermore, the CRP/GRP hybrid structure was found to be superior to any other GRP laminates in fatigue properties. The failure of those hybrids took place stepwise in slow motion. Therefore, it was confirmed that the CRP/GRP hybrid structure shows the excellent spring properties and can be used for a long time in a wide elastic region.

INTRODUCTION

Glass fiber reinforced plastics (GRP) have been widely used for structural and functional materials. And recently new reinforcement fibers, for instance, those of carbon, aramid, silicon-carbide, etc., have been developed and with these materials composite materials of still higher performance than before have been made available (1),(2). Especially, in line with the widening uses of high strength and elastic carbon fiber (CF), the CF/GF hybrid structure which combines CF and glass fiber (GF) is beginning to be used so widely for many applications. Therefore, studies on the CF/GF hybrid structure are now reviewed from the broad standpoint which covers the application field, for instance, the designing of material not to mention about mechanical properties (3-5). Meanwhile, high functional materials which take advantage of high elastic modulus and light weight of CF will present an important theme for study in the future development of CF/GF hybrid materials.

Here, with the prepreg sheets of CF and GF as the bases, several kinds of CF/GF hybrid and CRP composites are designed with the flexural rigidity equal to that of conventional GRP to study the flexural rigidity, elastic modulus and flexural strength (6). In designing the hybrid structure, we adopted the beam theory and further by applying the graphical method, the number of laminating layers was determined. For the hybrid structures thus obtained, elastic modulus and flexural strength are calculated theoretically, which are then compared with those obtained by the test to see validity of analytical results. Then, based on the developments of such fundamental theories, we have studied the fatigue pro-

perty of various kinds of hybrid structures and CRP composites. Further, with regard to the fatigue strength of various kinds of CF/GF hybrid structures and CRP composites, the value was estimated to study validity of analytical results.

Table 1 Specification of GF and CF prepreg-sheet

Type of Prepreg-sheet	Reinforcement	Matrix	Thickness (mm)	Elastic modulus (kgf/mm ²)
G F	Glass fiber (Nittobo, RS 120 E-601)	Epoxy resin (Toray, #2500)	0.40	E _g = 4730
C F	Carbon fiber (Torayca T300)	ditto	0.21	E _c = 13070

$$\beta = E_c/E_g = 2.76$$

DESIGNING HYBRID COMPOSITES WITH THE RESPECTIVELY EQUAL FLEXURAL RIGIDITY

Number of Plies of CF/GF Prepreg-Sheet

Hybrid composites in this paper are of the CRP/GRP sandwich construction, and are laminated by using the prepreg-sheet of carbon fiber(CF) and glass fiber(GF) shown in table 1. Number of plies is determined by the following method. Determining the needed value of the flexural rigidity of hybrid composites, (EI)_{Hy} (E_{Hy} = bh³/12), as shown in Fig. 1, its flexural rigidity is given by the equation of

$$(EI)_{Hy} = E_g I_g + E_c I_c \tag{1}$$

where E_g and E_c respectively show the elastic modulus of GRP and CRP, while I_g and I_c respectively show the second moment of area in GRP and CRP parts and β are represented as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} I_g &= b(h_g)_o^3 n_g^3 / 12 \\ I_c &= b[\{ (h_c)_o n_c + (h_g)_o n_c \}^3 - (h_g)_o^3 n_c^3] / 12 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

where (h_g)_o is the thickness of GF prepreg-sheet and n_g is its number of plies, and (h_c)_o and n_c in CF are defined similarly.

In this paper, the mechanical properties of hybrid composites are compared with those of GRP only. So, if taken the second moment of area of GRP only as I* = b(h_g)_o³ n^{*3} / 12 (n*: number of plies of GRP only), from the relationship of β(EI)_{Hy} = E_g I* + E_c I_c, as derived from Eqs.(1) and (2), the equation of number of plies is obtained as follows.

$$\alpha_c = \alpha_o [\{ (1 - \alpha_g^3) / \beta + \alpha_g^3 \}^{1/3} - \alpha_g] \tag{3}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_o &= (h_c)_o / (h_g)_o & \beta &= E_c / E_g \\ \alpha_c &= n_c / n_g^* & \alpha_g &= n_g / n_g^* \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

Fig. 2 shows the calculation diagram of number of plies for hybrid composites. The α_c-α_g diagram of right side in Fig. 2 is the result of Eq.(3), while

Fig. 1 Cross-section of sandwich-typed CRP/GRP hybrid composites.

Fig. 2 Calculation diagram for obtaining the laminate constitution of CRP/GRP hybrid composites with the respectively equal flexural rigidity.

α_c - n_g^* diagrams of left side are written with n_c as a parameter. Here, the usage of Fig. 2 is explained when it is used for calculating the number of plies for the CF and GF prepreg sheets used for the hybrids of equal flexural rigidity shown in Table 1 for example. First, if it is assumed that $n_g^*=9$ plies is the number of plies of GRP only to satisfy the relation of $(EI)_{Hy} = E_g I_g^*$, and then, as shown in Fig. 2, the scale of $\alpha = 0-1.0$ is exchanged with the scale of $n_g = 0-9$ plies. Next, a horizontal line is drawn to the left from the intersection of the line of $n_g^*=9$ plies and the n_c , the number of plies in the α - n_g^* diagram. Then a line is drawn perpendicularly to the n_g axis from the intersection on the α - α diagram. Here, as n_g is an integer, the n_g value near the perpendicular line is calculated as the number of plies of the GRP part.

Elastic Modulus

The equation of the elastic modulus of hybrid composites, E_{Hy} , is obtained from Eqs.(1) and (2) as follows.

$$E_{Hy}/E_g = \beta[1-(1-1/\beta)(1+\alpha)^{-3}] = \beta[1-(1-1/\beta)\Phi_1] = \beta[1-\Phi_2] = \beta\Phi_3 \quad (5)$$

where α is the factor of laminate constitution, and is put in

$$\alpha = \alpha_0 n_c / n_g \quad (6)$$

Fig. 3 shows the calculation diagram of E_{Hy}/E_g on log scale illustrated from Eq.(5). First, the fundamental line, which calculates the second () term in Eq.(5), $\Phi_1 = (1+\alpha)^{-3}$, is drawn as shown above in Fig. 3(a). Then, from the elastic modulus of the component material of the hybrid composites, the value of $(1-1/\beta)$ is calculated. For instance, assuming $\beta=2.76$, the equation Φ_2 is $\Phi_2 = 0.638\Phi_1$. Then, a line is drawn parallel to the fundamental line of Φ_1 and passing the point of 0.638 on the Φ_2 axis. The value of $(1+\alpha)$ of the hybrid composites with determined laminate constitution is spotted on the straight Φ_2 line, from which the Φ_3 axis on the right hand side can be read. Thus, the value in parenthesis [] in Eq.(5) is calculated. From this, the elastic modulus of the hybrid composites can be read on the Φ_3 - E_{Hy}/E_g diagram shown in Fig. 3(b). Here, the Φ_3 - E_{Hy}/E_g diagram is illustrated as such that, on the β axis shown on the straight $\Phi_3=1$ line, $\beta=2.76$ is situated. Then a straight line is drawn to

(a)

For example, the values of α for symbols, a, b and c, are respectively

$$\alpha_a = 0.15 \quad \alpha_b = 0.27 \quad \alpha_c = 1.05$$

(b)

Fig. 3 Calculation diagram for E_{Hy}/E_g .

pass this point with a slope of $b/a=1/2$ (because the scale of horizontal axis is twice greater than that of the vertical one). Then it is possible to read the value of E_{Hy}/E_g of each hybrid composite from the $\phi_3 - E_{Hy}/E_g$ diagram and also from the ϕ_3 values E_g which have been obtained from the laminate E_g constitution of each hybrid composite.

Strength

The fracture by bending of hybrid composites of sandwich construction will take place at the facing CRP parts or the core GRP part. However, there will be no shear breakage showing at the CRP/GRP interface due to small value of $\alpha = \alpha_c n_c / n_g$.

First, if the facing CRP part fails due to the bending moment of M_c , and then the flexural stress in CRP part, σ_c , is obtained by

$$\sigma_c = \beta M_c h / 2(I_g + \beta I_c) \quad (7)$$

And the flexural stress of hybrid composites, σ_{Hy} , is then given by

$$\sigma_{Hy} = M_c h / 2I_{Hy} \quad (8)$$

Here, eliminating M_c from Eqs. (7) and (8), σ_{Hy} is

$$\sigma_{Hy} = (I_g + \beta I_c) \sigma_c / \beta I_{Hy} \quad (9)$$

Next, in case of failure at the core GRP part, σ_{Hy} is similarly obtained as follows.

$$\sigma_{Hy} = h(I_g + \beta I_c) \sigma_g / h I_g I_{Hy} \quad (10)$$

Further, it is considered that the both facing CRP and core GRP fail at the same time. The critical factor of laminate constitution at that time, α_{cr} , is

obtained from Eqs.(9) and (10) as the same strength as follows.

$$\alpha_{cr} (= \alpha_o (n_c/n_g)_{cr}) = \zeta/\beta - 1 \quad (11)$$

where ζ is the strength ratio, $\zeta = \sigma_c/\sigma_g$. Therefore, the failure of hybrid composites occurs at the facing CRP part in region of $\alpha > \alpha_{cr}$, in contrast with this, at core GRP part in region of $\alpha < \alpha_{cr}$, respectively.

Furthermore, for producing the diagram on the strength design of hybrid composite, Eqs.(9) and (10) are reviewed with the laminate constitution, α shown in Eq.(6). As this result, arranging in ratio of strength of hybrid composites, σ_{Hy} , to that of GRP only, σ_g , these equation are represented as follows.

$$\text{In case of failure of CRP part } (\alpha \geq \alpha_{cr}) \\ \sigma_{Hy}/\sigma_g = \zeta [1 - (1 - 1/\beta)(1 + \alpha)^{-3}] = \zeta \Phi_3 \quad (12)$$

$$\text{In case of failure of GRP part } (\alpha \leq \alpha_{cr}) \\ \sigma_{Hy}/\sigma_g = \beta(1 + \alpha) [1 - (1 - 1/\beta)(1 + \alpha)^{-3}] = \beta(1 + \alpha) \Phi_3 \quad (13)$$

Accordingly, Fig. 4 shows the calculation diagrams illustrated from Eqs.(12) and (13). Since, what are described in the parenthesis of Eqs.(12) and (13) are the same as those in Eq.(5), the illustration to obtain the Φ_3 value shown in Fig. 3(a) is purposely omitted here. And as shown in Fig. 4(a) and (b), the β axis in Fig. 3 is replaced by the ζ or $\beta(1 + \alpha)$ axis. For example, if $\zeta = 3.5$ and $\beta = 2.76$, from the Eq.(11), α_{cr} will be 0.27, therefore, with $\alpha \geq \alpha_{cr}$, the failure will be on the facing material. And by drawing a straight line of $\zeta = 3.5$ which a slope of $b/a = 1/2$ on the calculation diagram of $\Phi_3 - \sigma_{Hy}/\sigma_g$ in Fig. 4(a), the value of σ_{Hy}/σ_g will be obtained for the hybrid composite with the laminate constitution of $\alpha \geq \alpha_{cr}$. Then, where $\alpha < \alpha_{cr}$, using Fig. 4(b), the value of σ_{Hy}/σ_g is shown on the $\Phi_3 - \sigma_{Hy}/\sigma_g$ diagram in the drawing. By first obtaining the value of $\beta(1 + \alpha)$ from the $(1 + \alpha) \Phi_3 = \beta(1 + \alpha)$ diagram, it is possible to obtain σ_{Hy}/σ_g the same way before.

Meanwhile, results of Figs. 3 and 4 are applicable for all laminated composites so long as they are the sandwich type hybrid composites not to mention about hybrid laminates of the same flexural rigidity. Therefore, on the contrary to the method described here, it is also possible to obtain the laminate constitution of a hybrid composite from the strength required.

SPECIMEN AND TEST METHOD

Table 2 shows the laminate constitution of three hybrid composites, GRP and CRP used as specimens in this paper. Here, these composites were designed from the calculation diagram shown in Fig. 2, based on the needed flexural rigidity of

(a) in case of failure of CRP part.

(b) in case of failure of GRP part.

Fig. 4 Calculation diagram for obtaining σ_{Hy}/σ_g .

GRP($n^*=9$ plies). Then, molding condition is, press-cure 7 kgf/mm² at 120 °C for 1 hr, and post-cure 130 °C for 2 hrs. Further, on the thickness of specimens, as shown in Table 2, the measured thickness (mean of specimens) is nearly equal to the desired thickness, which is quite satisfactory. Meanwhile, the fiber content is $V_f=60\%$ for all composites.

Flexural testing was done in 4-point bending (support span:120 mm, load span:60 mm) under loading speed of 2.5 mm/min. Fatigue testing was in the completely reversed plane bending with constant load, using the dumbbell type specimen. Cyclic loading was applied at a frequency of 30 Hz. Then, the peak-to-peak value of deflection was continuously recorded.

RESULTS AND EVALUATION

Flexural Properties

Table 3 shows the elastic modulus of CRP/GRP hybrid composites. The calculated values, E_{cal} , were obtained from the calculation diagram shown in Fig. 3, and were a little different from the experimental results, E_{exp} . Even so, the elastic modulus can be obtained with a high accuracy for each hybrid composites.

Table 4 shows the ratio of the flexural rigidity of hybrid composites to its needed value. The calculated values of Hy-A and -B are a little larger than the needed value except for Hy-C, resulting in the result of the α_n diagram shown in Fig. 2. But, these values as a whole show comparatively a good agreement with experimental. Hence, it is suggested that this calculated method can be used for the design of flexural rigidity of hybrid composites.

Tables 5 and 6 show the flexural strength of specimens shown in Table 2. The calculated values in Table 6 were obtained from the calculation diagram shown in Fig. 4(a) (because of $\alpha > \alpha_{cr}$) using the results of Tables 1 and 5. Therefore, three CRP/GRP hybrid composites described in this paper fail at each facing CRP part. The calculated values of Hy-A and -B were a little smaller than of experimental, and that of Hy-C was a little larger. And the ratio of these values is not as good a coincident as the results of elastic modulus.

Table 6 Flexural strength for CRP/GRP hybrid composites.

Hybrid	$(\sigma_{pl})_{exp}$	$(\sigma_b)_{exp}$	$(\sigma_{pl})_{cal}$	$(\sigma_b)_{cal}$	$(\sigma_{pl})_{cal}$	$(\sigma_b)_{cal}$
	(kgf/mm ²)	(kgf/mm ²)	(kgf/mm ²)	(kgf/mm ²)	$(\sigma_{pl})_{exp}$	$(\sigma_b)_{exp}$
Hy-A	61.5	108.1	51.9	90.7	0.844	0.839
Hy-B	79.3	131.3	69.4	121.4	0.875	0.925
Hy-C	76.2	139.1	82.7	144.6	1.085	1.040

Table 2 Constitution of CRP/GRP hybrid, GRP and CRP composites.

Specimen	Constitution	No. of plies	Thickness(mm)	
			Desired	Measured
GRP		9	3.60	3.66
Hy-A		1/7/1	3.22	3.06
Hy-B		2/5/2	2.84	2.73
Hy-C		3/3/3	2.46	2.53
CRP		12	2.52	2.61

Table 3 Elastic modulus for CRP/GRP hybrid composites.

Hybrid	E_{exp}	E_{cal}	$\frac{E_{cal}}{E_{exp}}$
	(kgf/mm ²)	(kgf/mm ²)	
Hy-A	7460	7580	1.016
Hy-B	9810	10150	1.035
Hy-C	11060	12090	1.093

Table 4 Evaluation of flexural rigidity for hybrid composites.

Hybrid	$\frac{EI}{(EI)_{GRP}}$	
	Experimental	Calculated
Hy-A	0.969	1.148
Hy-B	0.905	1.054
Hy-C	0.811	0.816

$(EI)_{GRP}$: Needed value

Table 5 Flexural strength for CRP and GRP.

Material	Strength	
	Propor. limit σ_{pl} (kgf/mm ²)	Breaking σ_b (kgf/mm ²)
G F	58.1	131.7
C F	89.3	156.2

Nevertheless, it is suggested that this illustrated method can substantially estimate the flexural strength of CRP/GRP hybrid composites.

Fatigue Properties

EI/(EI)₀-N diagram. Fig. 5 shows the reduction curve of flexural rigidity (EI/(EI)₀-N diagram) of GRP, CRP and all specimens, respectively. In case of GRP only, with reduction of flexural rigidity exceeding 20%, the rigidity is quickly decreased to fracture. While, the value of EI/(EI)₀ of CRP only gradually reduces till about 30%. Then, here is described the behavior of fatigue fracture at this time. No failure of fibers in the surface layer was observed, but over the thickness direction, the cracking grew from both the notched sections diagonally left and right to the neutral direction. Therefore, this cracking is assumed to have caused the reduction of rigidity. Particularly, from the fact that both GRP only and CRP only after the fatigue test exhibited delamination, it is assumed that the point of rapid decrease of rigidity, which in other words is the ultimate fracture has been caused by the delamination. Next, in case of hybrid composites, unlike the cases of only GRP and CRP, the reduction of rigidity is evidently noticed when the value of EI/(EI)₀ is considerably high nearly as 0.92 except for Hy-C. This is understood that the CRP part fractures like that of only CRP, however, the CRP parts of both hybrid composites are relatively thin, crackings from the notched areas grow faster and reach the CRP/GRP interface and that cracking also causes delamination at the CRP/GRP interface. In case of Hy-C, on the other hand, the fracture behavior is similar to that of Hy-A and -B, but CRP part is thicker. Then it is assumed that the cracking has grown sufficiently to have the EI/(EI)₀ curve indicate the similar tendency of CRP only. Meanwhile, no fracture has been observed at GRP part of all these hybrid composites.

Fig. 5 EI/(EI)₀-N diagrams.

Fig. 6 S - N diagrams.

S - N diagram. Fig. 6 shows S-N diagrams of all specimens. At this time, number of cycles to failure, N, is measured as EI/(EI)₀=0.8 in Fig. 5, according to Japanese Industrial Standard (JIS) K7119. Fatigue strength becomes large in the order of Hy-A, -B and -C, as shown in Table 7, resulting in CF content. And the

value of $(\sigma_f)_{cal}$, based on fatigue strength of CRP only at $N=10^7$ cycles, is obtained from the calculation diagram of Fig. 4(a). Here, the value of $(\sigma_f)_{exp}$ of only CRP is 55.0 kgf/mm², and that of only GRP is 27.5 kgf/mm². Consequently, the calculated values were close to the values obtained by experiments. Therefore, it is indicated here that the fatigue strength can be estimated with a fairly high accuracy for the hybrid composites.

CONCLUSIONS

The static flexural and fatigue properties of CRP/GRP hybrid and CRP composites with equivalent flexural rigidity were studied based on the graphical method using the beam theory to determinate the construction of CRP/GRP hybrid composites. And then these results are applied to examine the fatigue properties of these composites and the properties of such the analytical results are confirmed by comparing them with the experimental ones. And so the summary of this study is shown as follows.

- 1) The design of the laminate construction of CRP/GRP hybrid composites with desired value of flexural rigidity is easily decided graphically by applying the beam theory and this method is confirmed that it affords a good accuracy.
- 2) The flexural modulus and strength of CRP/GRP hybrid and CRP composites to be designed are theoretically obtained by the graphical method and comparing the theoretical results with experimental ones, and it is confirmed that these values correspond each other.
- 3) The percent reduction of the flexural rigidity of CRP in fatigue process is slow and then quick reduction of flexural rigidity is not seen until the percent reduction is about 30%. But that of CRP/GRP hybrid composites is low as about 8% and beyond this level, no rapid reduction is seen yet.
- 4) Fatigue strength at $N=10^7$ cycles of CRP/GRP hybrid composites can be estimated by the fatigue strength of CRP used for surfacing. Particularly, it is interesting to note that the estimated fatigue strength of CRP/GRP hybrid composites, which is assumed as the fracture at CRP part, coincides with the experimental results with a fairly high accuracy.

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Table 7 Fatigue strength for CRP/GRP hybrid composites.

Hybrid	$(\sigma_f)_{exp}$ (kgf/mm ²)	$(\sigma_f)_{cal}$ (kgf/mm ²)	$(\sigma_f)_{cal}$ $(\sigma_f)_{exp}$
Hy-A	36.6	31.9	0.872
Hy-B	42.0	42.8	1.019
Hy-C	48.6	50.9	1.047

σ_f : Fatigue strength at $N=10^7$ cycles